

Circular sPrint Application form Questions categorized

Applicant Basic Information

- Name, surname, email address, country of residence, other contact details

The Occupation (The form can be split between industry professionals and researchers)

- Specify the occupation; student or professional
- Acquired degree
- Company or university,
- Field of the company or field of research
- Country of operation
- Role in the company

The Event Topic Related Knowledge

- Describe your knowledge on Circular Design, Additive Manufacturing, 3D modeling, FEM simulation
- Software skills and level: For example in 3D printing slicers, 3D modeling, simulation (Solidworks, Autodesk Fusion, Altair Inspire, Ansys, etc...)

The Motivation

- Why do you want to participate in the event?
- What are your expectations?

The Legislative Section

- I declare that the information provided by me in the application form is true and correct
- I have read and accept the Terms and Conditions (see <https://www.crafth.eu/terms-and-conditions>)
- I give my consent to the processing of my personal data and I declare I read the Privacy Policy (included in the Terms and Conditions)
- I want to receive updates about future editions of the Challenge and similar events

For a Company wishing to join or post a Challenge

- Specify the company, the field of the company, role in the company, country of operation
- Why would your company like to join?
- Do you already have a challenge in mind about 3D-printing for circularity?